

Assessment of the Influence of small-scale Business on Academic Performance of Middle school Female Students in Takeita City, Zinder, Niger Republic

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to assess the influence of small-scale business on academic performance among middle school female students in Takeita City, Zinder, Niger Republic. A quantitative approach through an explanatory research design is used to conduct this study. The Population of the study consists of all middle school class two students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Takieta City, Zinder, Niger Republic. A sample size of 100 female students were selected using multi-stage sampling technique. The data were collected through a questionnaire and the results indicate that girls who daily engage themselves in Small Scale Business and devote much time in these activities are negatively influenced in their academic activities (school attendance, lesson review, homework, etc.). Although the social role that the small-scale business plays, it is undeniable that it constitutes an influencing factor which can leads the female students to dropout. That's why it is recommended to female students who practice that activity, to plan their time and respect this planning and to parents in order to control the practice of the extracurricular activities of their daughter. Parents must also ensure and place a particular emphasis on the follow up of the schooling of their daughter.

Keywords: Small Scale Business, Female Students, Academic Performance.

Introduction

Education plays a key role in the development of a country, so it would be fallacious to think about a development worthy of its name without it. Indeed, the objective set by UNESCO (1990 as cited in Abdou, 2020, p.12) during the world conference on education in Jomtien (Thailand) on Education For All (EFA) to which Niger subscribed in 2000, caused the swelling of the school population and a massive transition from primary to lower secondary education. Regarding the importance of education in the development of each country, Niger Republic has placed a particular emphasis on the development of education since its accession to independence. Thus, to improve this education system, several reflections have been carried out in order to meet the aspirations of the population of Niger, which must participate fully in its economic and socio-cultural development. In 1998, Niger adopted a law (LOSEN) which carried the orientation of the educational system of Niger (Law n°98-12 of June 1st 1998). This law was materialized by the elaboration of a decennial program for the development of education (PDDE) for the period of 2003-2013. Indeed, this law promoted the expansion of secondary school enrollment while creating an imbalance between needs and available means. Despite all the efforts made, the educational system of Niger republic is still confronted with gender disparities. The schooling and the academic success of the young girls, is far behind those of the boys. Those disparities are for the most parts, related to socio-cultural and economic factors. Many studies (Roufai, 2011; Quenum, 2011 ; Zah, 2013) particularly supported the idea that traditional status of the girl/woman, the economic situation of the parents, the domestic work, the small scale business, the forced and early marriage, the undesired pregnancy constitute some causes of these gender inequalities in terms of access, performance and school completion. Considering the importance of girls' education, this study focuses on assessing the Small-Scale Business on Academic Performance among Middle School Female students in Takeita City, Zinder, Niger Republic.

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This article focuses on the academic performance of girls, which falls within the field of social science studies and several methodological approaches. Study carried out by Jacques HALLAK (1981) revealed that factors like social factor, geographical factor and environmental factor constitute the main factors of school success. The family environment has a direct influence on the academic performance of students. It's also shown that students from privileged backgrounds, given their social conditions, obtain more good school results than those from disadvantaged parents, Abdou (2020, p.48). ZAH (2013), found that the school failure of the students can be justified by the socio-economic status of their parents. Other studies (UNICEF, 1990; Daniel, 2014; Johannes, 2018) revealed the influence of school environment, culture, and peers on the academic performance of girls. It is asked in the schooling of girls the reasons of the poor school attendance of girls in these terms: how to explain that there are traditionally so few girls in schools in Niger? The desire of mothers to keep their daughters by their side, early marriage encouraged by the culture, fear of the influence of the modern school on children by parents and the unfavorable perception of school that girls have due to failures perpetrated by many students are the reasons of the poor school attendance of girls mentioned UNICEF (1990). The solution to this scourge in UNICEF's approach is to raise public awareness of the benefits of educating their daughters as well as the success of some of them at all school levels.

According to World Bank (2018, p.26) "In the global context, young girls' education, lagging behind that of boys, remains the major concern of the international community in general, and that of Africa in particular". Among the problems that affect the educational system and secondary education in African societies appears the poor academic performance of girls (Abdou, 2020 p.17). The extracurricular activities of girls are becoming more and more intensive and are affecting their academic performance as supported by the study carried by Koura (2001) and Roufai (2011). Despite the multiple efforts that educational policy makers are combining in collaboration with the Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) for the smooth running of the system, the educational future of girls remains worrying. In fact, in the program to accelerate the schooling and academic success of girls in the cross-border areas of UEMOA area, the commission concluded that, "if access to education is an imperative, making the students succeed remains the final objective" (UEMOA, 2011 p. 58). The follow up of the UEMOA aims, in the long term, to strengthen the role of women in regional integration through an improvement in the educational offer, particularly in cross-border areas. All these efforts made by State members, their partners and international organizations are undeniable and improvement has been made, but the objectives are far from being achieved. The challenges that face the education sector today, are therefore enormous. In addition to schooling, the matter of young girls' school retention, their success and above all their quality supervision remains problematic (UEMOA, 2011 p.59). According to Proteau (1995, p.75) "In Ivory Coast Republic, although the significant efforts made since independence, their educational situation is not fundamentally different from that of other African countries, particularly with regard to gender inequalities".

Table1: School enrollment rates in Ivory Coast Republic

Areas	First cycle of Secondary School		Secondary High School	
	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls
National level	40.7%	21.8%	19.9%	8.2%
Abidjan	52.9%	29.9%	25.1%	12.7%

Source: Data from RESEN (2010)

Like other countries, Niger is also facing problems related to illiteracy, low school performance of girls, and school retention (Roufai et al, 2011; Abdou, 2020). This problem continues to persist and hinders the retention of girls in schools. For example, the General Census of Population and Housing (RGPH) in Niger of 2012 shows a proportion of 55.6% of the population of 15 years and plus having no level of education, 62.69% of them are female. For the proportion of schooled children, it registers a significant decline according to the level. At the secondary level, according to the school census 2005-2006 carried out by the Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Technology, the number of students almost doubled, going from 92,463 to 179,721 students in 2005-2006. But these numbers do represent only 17.1% of the population of children of school age; the enrollment rate was 17.1% in 2005-2006.

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Table 2: Statistical report of school enrollment

Years	School Enrollment	
	Boys	Girls
2014-2015	93%	7%
2015-2016	91.4%	8.6%

Source: Statistical report 2015-2016

Thus, the last statistical report in table 2, shows that the girls' enrollment rate has increased of 1.6%. However, the rate increase remains high for boys. At the secondary school level, the poor academic performance of girls is also observed (Abdou 2023, Abdou & al. 2021). This situation is more accentuated and more recurrent in rural areas where girls' access to school is very low. This educational challenge requires careful analysis in order to find adequate solutions so that the secondary school level contributes to the production of human capital. This is why the government of Niger Republic created a law which carries the Orientation of the Educational System of Niger (LOSEN, law n°98-12 of June 1, 1998), because education is a right for all Nigeriens and the State guaranteed to children from 4 to 18 years old. The same law specifies that secondary school education receives children aged of 11 to 13 and its normal duration is 4 years. This sub-sector of secondary education is taken into account by the law and texts, but despite all these, exhaustive challenges are observable. The most noted challenge is the school dropout caused by the poor academic performance of female students (Abdou 2020, p.18), excluding each year a significant number of learners. Regarding this situation, the following research questions are asked.

Objective of the study

1. Assess the influence of small-scale business enrolment on academic performance of female students in middle schools in Takieta, Niger.
2. Assess the influence of time devoted for small scale businesses on academic performance among female students in middle schools in Takieta, Niger.

Research Questions

1. Do the female students who practice small scale business perform well at middle schools in Takieta, Niger?
2. Do the female students who devote much time to small scale businesses perform well at middle schools in Takieta, Niger?

Hypotheses

1. Girls who do small scale businesses do not perform well at school.
2. Girls who devote much time to small scale businesses do not perform well at school.

Methodology

This study was conducted using a quantitative approach through an explanatory research design as the study seeks to assess the correlation between small scale business practice and academic performance and time allotted to small scale business and academic performance. In this case, the academic performance is measured through the grades of the students. The Population of this study consists of all middle school class two students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Takieta city, zinder, Niger Republic. A representative sample of 100 female students which corresponds to 50% of the total number of the female students of that school was selected using multi-stage sampling technique. Considering the quantitative nature of this study, the data were collected through a questionnaire and analysed through SPSS and Excel software.

Results

Research Question

Do the female students who practice small scale businesses perform well at middle schools in takieta, Niger?

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Table 3: Statistical analysis of research question 1

Indicators	Do you have a good school performance?			
	Yes	No	Total	Percent
Do you practice the small trading?				
Yes	12	31	43	43%
No	41	16	57	57%
Total	53	47	100	
Percent	53%	47%	100%	100%

Source: Field Data (2021)

The results in Table 3 show the relationship between the small-scale business practice and school performance of the students. It is clear that, among the 43% of respondents who practice small scale business, only 28%, of them have good results and can have good school performance, compared to 72% who do not have good results and who do not even think they have a good academic performance. These results indicate that small scale business has a negative effect on the school performance of female students. So these data confirm the hypothesis no. 1 according to which: “Girls who do small scale businesses do not perform well at school.”. As a result, the poor school performance of girls results from the practice of small scale.

Research Question 2

Do the female students who devote much time to small scale businesses perform well at middle schools in takieta, Niger?

Table 4: Statistical analysis of research question 2

Indicators	How much time do you devote to the exercises?					
	None of them	1 to 2 hours	Total	Percent	Cumulated Percent	
How much time do you spend to small scale business?	None of them	20	37	57	57%	57%
	2 to 4 hours	39	03	42	42%	99%
	More than 4 hours	01	00	01	1%	100%
Total	60	40	100			
Percent	60%	40%	100%	100%		

Source: Field Data (2021)

The table 4 shows the influence of time devoted daily to small trading compared to that devoted to school exercises. In fact, the results of the survey show that, among the 100 students surveyed, among whom 43 students practice petty trade. It can be seen that only 7% of them devote approximately one to two hours of time to school activities, compared to more than 91%, who do not exercise but who devote more than 3 hours of time in their extracurricular activities. This situation has direct consequences on their academic performance and manifests itself mainly in the accumulation of bad grades. Thus, clearly and especially taking into account this table 4, we notice that the time devoted to exercises is insignificant compared to that devoted to small business. So this remark, based on the interpretation of the results, confirms hypothesis no. 2, which according to which “girls who devote time to petty trade unlike that of school activities cannot have a good academic performance”. Therefore, the more female students devote their time to petty trade, the greater their chance of having a good poor performance.

Discussion of Findings

This part presents previous works and studies that had the same or similar results with this study. The involvement and daily participation of students in small commerce can be a factor that affects the academic results of learners. Indeed, girls are the most involved in small trading and devote more time to it. Thus, the results of this study clearly show that girls who devote more time to small trading than to school activities, do not have good results and suddenly, they cannot have a good academic performance. This study is corroborated with that of ROUFAI et al. (2011). These situations have direct consequences on the school performance of the girls and are manifested essentially by a drastic and radical drop of grades in classes. They thus begin to accumulate bad grades linked to the many shortcomings and insufficiencies they have accumulated; partly related to the lack of concentration and attendance and lack of mastering the courses received.

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Still for ROUFAI et al. (2011), a girl forced to do a variety of domestic chores every day, apart from her school obligations, is no longer able to correctly and fully follow the lessons given in class. Even if the work is done moderately by the girl and adjusted so that she only works outside school hours (i.e. before or after the start of classes and/or on weekends), she cannot escape to physical fatigue, to the point where it will be impossible for him to attend school properly. Often, the girl is forced to go to school late and unlike these friends who arrived on time, she will have followed only part of the lessons that she should have followed in full if she was on time. In this same sense, the results are similar to the results of the Report Africa 2012 elaborated by the International Organization PLAN (2012) entitled “*Because I am a Girl*”. This study was carried out in 11 African countries between November 2011 and May 2012. These results showed that for many children across Africa, finding enough time to study is a constant struggle against the daily works done for their survival and that of their families. This study found that it is difficult for learners to concentrate in class or to study well at home. Consequently, the pressure of the tasks to be accomplished is an essential factor limiting the academic success of girls. In addition, the results of this survey corroborates the results of SINON (2010) and Quenum (2011) who found that the time devoted to domestic chores outside of school hours influences the school performance of girls.

Conclusion

Ultimately, it is important to note that the practice of small trading by school girls is culturally spread widely in Niger. This is why it is traditionally believed that the small trading of girls has a socializing character because it initiates girls to support themselves and help their parents. However, this activity represents an influencing factor of academic performance and school retention of the girls. The results of this study indicates that the involvement of female students in small trading is considerably more important than in their school activities. Further these results show that the practice of these extracurricular activities is much more frequent among girls from low-income families. Therefore, the low level of education and socio-economic status of parents can be and explanation to the practice of small trading by school girls.

Recommendation

In view to the results presented, the following recommendation can play an important role in overcoming the problem of poor school performance of school girl due to the practice of small trading.

1. The female students who practice that activity, must plan their time and respect this planning;
2. Parents have to control the time of practicing the extracurricular activities of their daughter;
3. Parents must ensure and place a particular emphasis on the follow up of the schooling of their daughters;
4. They must also become more involved in the management of establishments through their representation and participation in the COGES and the AEP in order to know the role assigned to them in helping their children to improve their school performance;
5. They must also go to school from time to time in order to know the situation or the school work of their daughters.

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